

Adducts of Lanthanide(III) Glycolates with Neutral Ligands

(Ms.) S. GHOSH and B. PRADHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

Manuscript received 9 March 1994, revised 27 June 1994, accepted 22 July 1994

In pursuit of our systematic investigation on preference and stabilisation of coordination number and geometry by various lanthanide ions under the influence of varying ligand fields, the coordination behaviour of trivalent lanthanides in presence of glycolic acid and a neutral ligand is reported under the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table I) are consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The zero value of molar conductance of the complexes indicates that they are non-electrolytes. Their magnetic moment values (Table I) show little deviation from the Van Vleck values¹, indicating thereby that *4f*-electrons do not participate in bond formation. Thus the magnetic moments of these complexes are within the normal predicted range². The molecular weight measurement indicate monomeric nature of the compounds.

The ir spectra of the complexes contain all the fundamental and combination modes of coordinated ligands. Bands due to glycolic acid were obtained at 1 060 (C–OH), 1 575–1 590 (C=O) and 1 370–1 380 cm^{-1} (C–O). The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ bands of glycolic acid shifted to lower frequency regions upon complexation³. The strong bands at $\sim$ 1 250, 855 and 740 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of free *p*-picoline-*N*-oxide are assigned to the above three fundamental vibrations. The $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ band in the complexes occurred at 1 200–1 215 cm^{-1} . The shifting of this band from 1 250 cm^{-1} in the free ligand to the lower frequency is attributed to a change in N–O bond order as a result of oxygen-metal coordination⁴. The N–O bending vibration in all the complexes occurred at 840–850 cm^{-1} . Hence this band shows a negative shift in all the complexes. This negative shift suggests that the mass effect due to coordinated metal ion on (N–O) out-weighs the effect due to coordination⁵. The $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ band of the ligand underwent

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	M.p °C	Analyses%: Found/(C alcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
		Metal	N	C	H	
[La(GLA) ₃ γ -picNO] (White)	160	28.59 (29.37)	2.89 2.96	29.97 30.44	3.96 4.02	Diamag.
[Ce(GLA) ₃ γ -picNO] (White)	124	28.95 (29.54)	2.84 2.95	30.02 30.37	3.84 4.01	2.46
[Pr(GLA) ₃ γ -picNO] (Greenish white)	121	28.69 (29.66)	2.84 2.95	30.01 30.31	3.82 3.99	2.49
[Nd(GLA) ₃ γ -picNO] (Pinkish white)	131	29.61 (30.15)	2.81 2.93	29.90 30.10	3.80 3.97	3.42
[Sm(GLA) ₃ γ -picNO] (Cream)	140	31.05 (31.04)	2.79 2.89	29.68 29.72	3.77 3.92	2.65
[Gd(GLA) ₃ γ -picNO] (White)	160	31.84 (32.02)	2.76 2.85	29.17 29.31	3.62 3.87)	7.23

a positive shift.

The visible spectral bands of the lanthanides are hypersensitive to stereochemistry⁶. The absorption bands of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} in the visible and near-uv region appear due to the transition from the ground levels 3H_4 and $^4I_{9/2}$ to the excited J -levels of $4f$ -configurations respectively. The observed red-shift indicates the participation of the metal $4f$ and ligand orbitals in the formation of covalent bonding⁷. The various bonding parameters were calculated⁸ from the absorption maxima of the complexes. The value of β being less than unity (~ 0.98), along with positive values of δ percent (~ 1.9) and $b^{1/2}$ (~ 0.009), suggest moderate covalent character of bonding between the metal ions and the ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

A mixture of ethanolic solution of the lanthanide(III) nitrate and glycolic acid (1 : 3 molar ratio) was stirred for 1 h. To it an ethanolic solution of γ -picoline- N -oxide was added in excess with stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h. The solids separated on cooling were washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

The metal contents were estimated as metal oxides. Magnetic moment was determined by Gouy method at room temperature. The conductance ($\sim 10^{-3}M$ nitrobenzene) was measured on a Systronics 303 conductivity meter. Electronic and infrared spectra were recorded on Elico-CL-54 and Shimadzu-408

spectrophotometers respectively. The molecular weight was measured by Rast's method using biphenyl as solvent.

Acknowledgement

The authors thanks C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for C, H and N analyses.

References

1. J. H. VAN VLECK and A. FRANK. *Phys. Rev.*, 1929, **34**, 1498.
2. M. C. JAIN, R. K. SHARMA, A. K. SRIVASTAVA and P. C. JAIN. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **42**, 1305; M. SRIVASTAVA and G. S. PANDEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 447.
3. K. NAKAMAI, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 313.
4. I. S. AHUJA and R. SINGH. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 561; J. V. QUAGLIANO, F. FUJITA, G. FRANZ, D. J. PHILIPS and S. Y. TYREE. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3770.
5. S. XIDA, J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. A. WALMSLEY and S. Y. TYREE. *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 189.
6. D. G. KARRAKER. *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **6**, 1863.
7. S. P. SINHA. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 2205; M. R. HUNT, A. G. KRUGER, L. SMIT and G. WINTER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 53.
8. D. E. HENRIE and G. R. CHOPPIN. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 477; S. P. SINHA. *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, **22**, 57.